

Diesel Particulate Filter Dynamic Filtration

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Abstract

Particulate matter (PM) emitted from diesel vehicles has serious threats to the global climate, environment, and human health. Diesel particulate filters (DPFs) are currently the only effective after-treatment technology for reducing PM emissions, making it crucial to evaluate their filtration and pressure drop performance using numerical methods. This study developed and validated a lumped model based on spherical packed bed theory and Darcy's law to describe the dynamic PM filtration process in DPFs. The model accurately predicts real-time characteristics such as wall porosity, soot load, and pressure drop. Additionally, it examines the influence of channel characteristics, monolithic size, and exhaust conditions on filtration and pressure drop performance. Results indicate that increasing cell density, wall thickness, DPF length, and diameter enhances filtration efficiency, while higher DPF inlet temperatures and exhaust mass flow rates negatively impact performance. Moreover, wall thickness, DPF diameter, and exhaust flow rate significantly affect total pressure drop. These findings enhance dynamic performance prediction in PM filtration and provide a theoretical foundation for optimizing DPF structures.

1. Introduction

Mobile source emissions have severe impacts on the global climate, environment, and human health, with automobiles being the main contributors. Diesel vehicles, in particular, are responsible for over 80% of nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions and 90% of particulate matter (PM) emissions from mobile sources. PM consists of solid particles and carbides produced as by-products of diesel combustion, while NO_x forms through the reaction of oxygen and nitrogen at high combustion temperatures [1]. The small particle size and high inhalability of PM from diesel exhaust allow it to penetrate deeply into the lungs, posing serious health risks [2]. Meanwhile, NO_x emissions significantly contribute to environmental issues such as photochemical smog and acid rain.[3]

In recent decades, significant progress has been made to mitigate PM and NO_x emissions from diesel vehicles, driven by increasingly stringent emission regulations [4-5]. Advances have been made in areas like alternative fuels, fuel additives, engine optimization, combustion strategies, and exhaust aftertreatment technologies. Diesel particulate filters (DPFs) have emerged as the most effective aftertreatment device for reducing PM emissions. These dense filters capture nano- to micron-sized particles, greatly reducing both the mass and number of particles in the exhaust [6-7]. Wall-flow honeycomb ceramic DPFs consist of parallel channels connected by porous substrate walls, with alternating ends of the channels blocked. As exhaust flows through these channels, PM is trapped and deposited on the porous walls. Over time, however, the filters accumulate particles and may develop

an ash layer that cannot be removed by regeneration, leading to excessive particle build up [11]. This build up can increase exhaust backpressure, resulting in engine performance degradation air intake and exhaust efficiency, compromising combustion, and resulting in substantial decreases in power, reliability, and even difficulties in engine starting [12]. As a result, periodic DPF regeneration is required to eliminate the accumulated soot. Precisely determining the timing of this regeneration is vital for ensuring safety and efficiency. Current methods for determining regeneration timing include those based on exhaust back pressure, mileage, fuel consumption, and driving duration. However, the soot accumulation process is complex, with various factors influencing how soot is deposited in the DPF. Accurately assessing the detailed distribution of soot within the filter walls is difficult without advanced testing and characterization tools. Furthermore, due to the DPF's unique honeycomb porous structure, real-time soot loading is challenging to measure directly using sensors or other equipment, so most current methods estimate soot loading indirectly. Understanding the collection mechanism, distinguishing filtration stages, and accurately predicting pressure drop and soot loading are critical for successful DPF operation, particularly regarding regeneration control and diagnostics [13]. Therefore, accurately simulating DPF filtration and pressure drop performance using numerical methods is essential [14]. The process of PM (particulate matter) loading in DPFs has been a key research focus, with many studies examining how exhaust particles percolate and deposit inside the filters. The spherical packed bed filtration theory, which assumes the filter medium consists of spherical collection units, is widely used for wall-flow honeycomb ceramic DPFs [15-16]. As illustrated in Figure 1, the centre of each spherical collection unit represents the solid portion, while the surrounding area corresponds to the porous part of the wall [17].

Fig. 1. Soot deposition evolution around the spherical packed bed unit collector.

When exhaust PM passes through the filters, it is first collected inside the porous medium wall, which is referred to as the deep-bed filtration stage [18]. Once the amount of soot deposited on the wall surface reaches a certain threshold, the PM starts accumulating as a particle layer on the filter inlet channels' surface. This stage is known as cake filtration, during which subsequent inflowing particles are difficult to enter the wall [19]. It is worth noting that between the deep-bed filtration stage and the cake filtration stage; there is a transitional filtration stage. In this stage, it is generally believed that soot grows in a dendritic or hill-like manner, developing from the interior of the wall to the surface of the inlet channel, until a uniform cake layer is formed. The particle filtration efficiency is directly influenced by various factors, including the average pore size, porosity, wall thickness, and substrate material of the porous medium [20]. The accumulation of soot and ash in the substrate wall results in a substantial increase in filtration efficiency throughout the deep-bed filtration stage. In addition, the cake-layer filtration stage is characterized by a progressive increase in cake layer thickness and gradually flattened filtration efficiency [21]. [22] Considered the influence of soot deposited on the surface of the porous medium on the formation of the cake layer and the cake filtration efficiency can be determined based on empirical data. Zhang et al. [23] proposed the wall saturation index to control the process of soot deposition during deep-bed filtration and distinguished the transitional stage and the cake filtration stage based on the critical porosity value and the formation of the cake layer. Gong et al. [24] established a heterogeneous multiscale filtration model and applied it to the simulation of

soot deposition in DPFs. The model incorporated the consideration of the probability density function (PDF) of DPF pore size distribution based on the packed-bed theory [25,26]. Established a quasi-two dimensional model based on the assumption of soot fragmentation [27].

The PM loading leads to the blockage of filter pores, resulting in decreased permeability. The DPF pressure drop is often used as a measure of PM load to assist in the design of effective DPF control strategies, thereby preventing excessive fuelling and incomplete regeneration [31,32]. Significant contributions have been made to the development of classical DPF pressure drop models [31,32]. In recent years, researchers have made notable improvements and extensions to this work. [33] Conducted experimental tests on different substrate materials, such as SiC, aluminium titanate, and acicular mullite, under various levels of PM loading. They also investigated the impact of catalytic coating on PM oxidation. Zhang et al. [34] developed a one-dimensional semi-open DPF pressure drop model and validated it using computational fluid dynamics tools. [35] Proposed a data-driven model that maps pressure signals to soot concentrations for the transient prediction of raw PM emissions. [36] Introduced an improved one-dimensional numerical model and derived formulas for inlet and outlet pressure drops to enhance the accuracy of pressure drop prediction. [37] Proposed a combined approach using filter layers (FLs) and a new algorithm based on fast Fourier transform to reduce transient pressure signal hysteresis and fluctuations in exhaust temperature and flow during the filtration process. [38] Proposed a pressure drop model that accounted for slip flow and shape correction, leading to improved prediction accuracy. [39] Developed a three-dimensional simulation and mathematical model for rotational diesel particle filters and explored the impact of flow factors, such as particle volume fraction, flow velocity, etc., on flow field uniformity.

2. Description of the dynamic filtration model

2.1. Definition of porous wall layers and collector cells

To characterize the deep-bed filtration phase, the porous medium wall is discretized into several slabs in this study, with the thickness of each slab constituting a tiny proportion of that of the wall. From the incoming surface of the first slab, the soot particles penetrate the porous medium and are continuously trapped until slab saturation. Meanwhile, the untrapped particles enter the next slab inevitably. This procedure continues until the residual soot escapes from the last slab and slips out of the DPF. This discrete processing method enables the real-time modelling of the proportion of wall with soot deposited and the clean proportion without. In addition, the cake layer is divided into two parts: soot layer and ash layer. The cross-sectional diagram of a unit square channel is shown in Fig. 2. Respectively, the particulate deposition mass of the soot layer and ash layer are denoted as N_s and N_a , their cross-sectional areas as T_s and T_a , the width of the initial single channel as α , the diameter and effective length of the DPF substrate as D and L , and the DPF cell density as σ (cpsi). It can be seen from Fig. 2 that.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{0.0254}{\sqrt{\sigma}} - \omega_w \\ \Delta\omega_w = \frac{1}{n}\omega_w \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} w_1 = (\alpha - 2(\omega_c + \omega_a)) \\ w_2 = \alpha \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} m_s = \rho_s A_s L \\ m_a = \rho_a A_a L \end{cases}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \omega_s = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha^2 - \frac{m_a}{\rho_a L}}}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{\alpha^2 - \left(\frac{m_s}{\rho_s} + \frac{m_a}{\rho_a}\right) \frac{1}{L}}}{2} \\ \omega_a = \frac{\alpha}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{\alpha^2 - \frac{m_a}{\rho_a L}}}{2} \end{array} \right.$$

where ρ_s and ρ_a is the deposition density of soot layer and ash layer respectively.

The total number of DPF inlet channels N_{ch} can be expressed as

$$N_{ch} = \frac{\pi D^2 \sigma_{cpism}}{8} = \frac{\pi D^2}{8(\alpha + \omega_w)^2}$$

As exhaust particles are continuously deposited inside the cell unit, the diameter of the central collector increases until it reaches saturation. The mass of soot collected by each spherical collector unit is calculated for estimating the variation in soot concentration. Therefore, the filtration efficiency of the porous substrate wall depends on the filtration efficiency of a single sphere. The spherical method is refined by the assumption that the porosity and the surface area to volume ratio of the DPF porous medium are the same as the spherical collector.

2.2. Correction of particle aggregates effective density

It is a simplified way to treat diesel particles as spheres in filter models, however, the actual engine-out particulates are fractal aggregates [40]. In order to improve the model prediction accuracy, the effective density of diesel particles needs to be considered [41]. The effective density relates the particle mass to mobility and is defined as the ratio of the particle mass to the volume of a spherical particle with the same mobility equivalent diameter [42, 43]. The particle mass m_p and the effective density.

$$m_p = K_m d_m^{D_m}$$

$$\rho_{eff, d_m} = \frac{\rho_0 C_{c, d_a} d_a^2}{C_{c, d_m} d_m^2}$$

where K_m is the particle mass constant, d_m is the mobility equivalent diameter, D_m is the mass-mobility scaling exponent, for spheres, $D_m = 1.5$, for highly irregular particles including soot aggregates, $D_m < 2$ and ρ_{eff} decreases with increasing d_m [44], d_a is the aerodynamic diameter, ρ_0 is the unit density, which is assumed to be 1000 kg/m³. C_c is the Cunningham slip correction factor, which is affected by particle size.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the wall-flow DPF monolith and particulate deposition structure.

Where λ is the gas mean free path, $c1$, $c2$ and $c3$ are empirical parameters. Therefore, a power-law relationship for the effective density of aggregates can be obtained as [45]

The value of D_m in published literature is shown in Table 1, it can be inferred that the effective density is negatively correlated with the particle size after logarithmization. For soot particles, the maximum possible effective density would be 1800 kg/m³, which is the material density of soot [46]. In this study, D_m and C were taken as the average value according to the previous test data [47] and were 2.437 and 9054.02, respectively. Therefore,

$$\rho_{eff} = 9065.02d_p^{-0.563}$$

2.3. Collecting mechanisms and filtration efficiency

The filtration model is enabled to calculate the overall filtration efficiency of DPF. This efficiency is determined by considering the particle size distribution of the PM emissions. Since it is assumed that the soot is collected within a spherical cell, the model takes into account three main collecting mechanisms: Brownian diffusion, interception, and inertial collision [16,52] It is worth noting that the gravitational deposition is another filtration mechanism, but it is not considered in this model due to its negligible impact on the overall efficiency in case of continuous air flow through the filters. Brownian diffusion refers to the unpredictable movement of particles due to the thermal motion of gas molecules [53]. As the particle size decreases, the importance of Brownian diffusion increases.

The interception parameter defined as the ratio between the particle size and unit collector diameter. The mechanism of inertial collision plays a crucial role in collecting large diameter particles, and its efficiency is also influenced by the velocity of the exhaust flow. The filtration efficiency of a single spherical

Table 1

Literature	Fuel type	D_m
Maricq et al. [48]	Diesel	2.24
Olfert et al. [49]	Diesel	2.22 ~ 2.76
Quiros et al. [42]	Diesel	2.58
Haralampous et al. [50]	Diesel	2.44
Tan et al. [26]	Diesel	2.479
Momenimovahed [51]	Diesel	2.16 ~ 2.54

Unit collector for inertial collisions nI is related to the particle Stokes number and can be defined as

$$n_i = \frac{P_i^2}{(P_i + 0.25)^2}$$

The PM filtration process in the DPF porous wall is achieved by the combined action of various collecting mechanisms. These mechanisms vary in their effectiveness depending on the particle size distribution and engine operation conditions. By taking into account the above three independent collecting mechanisms, the filtration efficiency of a single spherical unit collector n_{cell} can be determined.

In this study, the pore velocity of the exhaust gas u_i passing through each layer is considered as the characteristic velocity for the particles, due to the collectors' close proximity. By discretizing the porous wall into n slabs, the filtration efficiency of the i -th slab can be calculated based on the efficiency of a single spherical unit collector.

2.4. PM loading process and filtration regime

As mentioned above, the process of soot loading can be roughly categorized into three stages: deep-bed filtration, cake filtration, and a transitional stage intermediate between them. The evolution of these filtration stages is adequately reflected by the growth mechanism of collecting units within the DPF from a microscopic perspective.

2.4.1. Growth of the cell units

The growth of the spherical unit collector is illustrated in Fig. 3. As a result of Brownian diffusion, interception, and inertial collision, particles are continuously deposited onto the surface of the unit collector, leading to an increase in the accumulated soot mass. This increase in mass is accompanied by a corresponding change in the diameter of the unit collector, which can be described as

The collected soot mass inside the unit cell, ρ_w is the packing density of the soot inside the porous wall.

The filtration efficiency and properties of the filter wall will change as diameter of the collector increases, in particular, the local wall porosity and permeability will decrease, which is given by

2.4.2. Transition of filtration phases

As the deep-bed filtration continues, the empty space inside the filter wall gradually becomes smaller until the collector cells are completely filled, and the particles begin to grow and connect with adjacent pores on the wall surface in a hill-like pattern [54]. This transitional phase can have an impact on the immediate filtration performance and ultimately leads to significant improvement in both filtration efficiency and pressure drop. Once the transitional phase is completed, a uniform and dense cake layer, will be formed [55].

The saturation mass of the spherical unit cell is proportional to the volume difference between saturated and clean unit cell. This relationship can be expressed as

Fig. 3. The growth of the spherical unit collector from clean state (left) to loaded state (right).

where B is the percolation factor. In deep-bed filtration, it plays a crucial role in determining the maximum size to which the collector can grow. Once the collector reaches the maximum diameter (βD_{cell}), its size no longer changes regardless of the amount of PM deposition. The value of B is typically obtained from experimental data and usually falls within the range of 0.659 to 1. In this study, $B = 0.91$.

Characteristic parameters such as wall porosity, filtration efficiency, and pressure drop are important in determining the transition from deep-bed filtration to cake filtration. However, in this study, a saturation coefficient θ_{sat} is specifically used as a classification parameter to categorize the filtration regime and identify the transition point. It represents the percentage of the maximum deposition mass that has been achieved and is expressed as the filtration process, it can be quantitative and objective determined whether the deep-bed filtration has transformed into cake filtration, thus enhancing the understanding and analysis of the filtration process. When the value of θ_{sat} is larger than 0, it indicates the initiation of cake filtration. When θ_{sat} reaches a certain threshold value of 1, indicating a significant build-up of the cake layer, it can be concluded that the filtration regime has completely shifted to cake filtration.

To determine the cake filtration efficiency, a “two-layer” method proposed by Serrano et al. [56] assumed that the filtration efficiency of the cake layer is directly proportional to that of the porous wall. The growth of the cake layer is influenced by the limit saturation coefficient of the spherical unit collector Sl . When the saturation coefficient exceeds Sl , the cake layer starts to grow, and the growth rate depends on the cake filtration efficiency $\eta_{f,c}$. As the porous wall becomes fully saturated, the cake layer functions as a barrier, accumulating the incoming soot and increasing the thickness of the cake layer. During this phase, the filtration efficiency gradually approaches that of the porous wall.

However, it is important to note that this approach ignores the impact of the soot layer itself, acting as a porous medium, on the PM filtration. This limitation implies that its adaptability to different working conditions is restricted. For instance, in cases where the wall surface is relatively clean but a certain thickness of cake layer is present, which frequently occurs during partial regeneration of DPF, the method relying on the convergence of the cake layer on a saturated wall surface cannot accurately predict the effectiveness of the cake layer in collecting PM. Therefore, in this study, we decoupled the filtration efficiency of the cake layer from that of the wall layer and defined it through independent modeling. This means that the three particle collecting mechanisms within the cake layer were also considered. However, rather than discretized into multiple slabs, the cake layer was considered as a whole with a thickness of ω_c . The evolution of the filtration phase is shown in Fig. 4. As the cake layer grows, its permeability constantly changes [57], and the saturated cake filtration efficiency can be calculated. Moreover, taking into consideration that a small quantity of soot particles may slip into the wall layer, a limiting factor was incorporated as the limit of cake filtration efficiency. Therefore,

By applying this modeling principle, the transition from the deep-bed filtration to the cake filtration is seamlessly executed, and the impact of the transitional phase is fully reflected. The cake filtration occurs at a precise moment during the deep-bed filtration, when the soot manages to penetrate the interface between the wall and the inlet channel.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the filtration phase.

Consequently, regardless of how the wall is divided, the deposition of cake begins when the spherical collectors of the first discretized wall slab begin to grow. Subsequently, the process of further saturating of the wall layer and increasing the thickness of the cake layer occurs synchronously, until the interface between the wall and the outlet channel (i.e., the last discretized wall slab) reaches saturation. It is important to note that in this case, even if only a small quantity of soot still enters the wall from the cake layer, further in-wall deposition is impossible. As the slipped soot is carried away by the exhaust flow, a dynamic equilibrium of wall porosity and permeability is maintained, ensuring constant filtration efficiency.

3. Experimental setup

The tests were conducted via an engine test bench, which is depicted in Fig. 6. The employed engine was a 6-cylinder turbocharged and intercooled heavy-duty diesel engine that compliant with the BS6 regulations. A DOC + DPF + SCR aftertreatment system was adopted. To measure the concentration of particulate mass and particulate number (PN) upstream and downstream of the DPF, a micro soot sensor AVL MSS-483 and a particle counter AVL 489 were employed. Additionally, temperature sensors and pressure difference sensors were installed to monitor the inlet temperature and pressure drop across the DPF, respectively. To weigh the DPF, a high-precision electronic balance was utilized. Detailed information of the engine, aftertreatment, test device and fuel are shown in Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5, respectively

In order to obtain the necessary input and output quantities for parameter identification, experiments were conducted. The input quantities included exhaust temperature, exhaust mass flow rate, DPF inlet PM concentration and PN concentration. These variables are closely related to engine operating conditions and have a significant impact on the filtration performance of the DPF which is reflected in the output quantities, including pressure drop and collected soot mass, etc. Therefore, it is important to select appropriate operating conditions for bench tests. For this study, 15 different engine operating points were chosen, consisting of 3 speeds (1000 rpm, 1800 rpm, and 2400 rpm) and 5 torques (50 Nm, 100 Nm, 200 Nm, 300 Nm, 350 Nm). For each condition, the experimental data was sampled every 30 min. The stable value within this time interval was calculated. A total of 3 measurements were taken and the average value was obtained. The selected operating points covered the low to medium load regions of heavy-duty diesel engines while avoiding the high load region. There are several reasons behind this selection. Firstly, increasing the load will lead to higher fuel injection quantities, resulting in higher engine-out PM emissions. Excessive PM trapped within the DPF wall can quickly deteriorate its clean state, which makes the

calibration of kw0 difficult. Secondly, excessively high loads can generate a large amount of heat during fuel combustion, leading to significantly increased exhaust temperature. This high temperature, combined with the presence of NO₂ in the exhaust, can trigger thermal-type passive regeneration reactions that consume PM significantly, which can interfere with the estimation of PM loading levels as well as the calibration of DPF wall parameters. Therefore, the exhaust temperature of every operating point in this study is below 320 °C.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of the experimental system.

Table 2

Specifications of the engine.

Parameter	Specification/value
Number of cylinders	4
Fuel injection system	Common rail
Suction type	Turbocharged intercooler
Bore (mm)	90.9
Stroke (mm)	100
Displacement (L)	7.7
Rated power (kW)	250 @ 3200 rpm
Maximum torque (Nm)	350 @ 1400–1400 rpm
Idle speed (rpm)	850

Table 3

Specifications of the aftertreatment system.

Parameter	DOC	DPF	SCR
Material	Cordierite	SiC	Cordierite
Catalyst	Pt, Pd	–	Cu-SSZ-13
Diameter × length (mm×mm)	Φ250	Φ250	Φ250
Cell density (#/inch ²)	400	300	400
Wall thickness (mm)	0.10	0.18	0.10

Volume (L) 3.7 3.9 4.9

Table 4

Information of the test equipment.

Equipment	Specification	Manufacturer
Electric dynamometer	AVL DynoDur 330	AVL
Gas emission analyser	AVL AMA I60	AVL
Fuel consumption meter	AVL 735S/753C	AVL
Particulate counter	AVL 489	AVL
Micro soot sensor	AVL 483	AVL
Electronic weighing scale	MT-R	Phonix

Table 5

Properties of the pure diesel.

Fuel parameter	Reference	Result	Analytic method
Density, 20°C (kg/m ³)	810 ~ 845	842.4	GB/T 1884-2004
Sulfur (mg/kg)	<10	2.8	SH/T 0689 2000
Acidity (mg/100 mL)	<7	3.54	GB/T 258-2016
Cold filter plugging point (°C)	<4	7	NB/SH/T 0248-2019
Flash point (°C)	>60	75.0	GB/T 261-2021
Cetane index	>46	51.6	SH/T 0694-2007
Distillation, 50 % (°C)	<300	281.3	GB/T 6536-2010
Distillation, 90 % (°C)	<355	329.4	GB/T 6536-2010
Distillation, 95 % (°C)	<365	340.2	GB/T 6536-2010

In addition, after completing the measurement of one operating condition, an activity regeneration activity Was performed and maintained for 10 min to completely remove soot particles from the DPF. Subsequently, a scavenging process was followed until the exhaust temperature cooled down to the level of idle speed. By following these procedures, the necessary data for parameter calibration could be obtained accurately and reliably, with interference from the airflow and the residual PM eliminated.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Model verification

4.1.1. Prediction of PM loading rate at DPF inlet

By incorporating particle effective density, the inlet PM concentration for the DPF (with an average particle diameter of 75 nm) aligns well with experimental values, serving as a key input for the filtration model. This alignment allows for reliable estimations of PM flow rate under varying operating conditions. In the medium–high speed range, the prediction has an average error of 2.12%. However, at low speeds and high loads, accuracy decreases, with a maximum error of 9.64%, likely due to incomplete airflow development, resulting in locally non-uniform PM concentrations. Additionally, since the AVL MSS-483 sensor provides output in mg/m^3 , a conversion is required to obtain the time-dependent PM flow rate in mg/s , assuming a uniform PM distribution across the exhaust pipe cross-section at the measurement point.

4.1.2. Calibration of clean wall permeability

To eliminate the impact of soot deposition on calibrating the clean wall permeability, k_{w0} , the inlet particulate matter (PM) concentration of the DPF was set to zero. Using data such as exhaust flow rate, pressure drop, and substrate parameters, k_{w0} was calculated, resulting in an average value of $3.384 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$ in this study. Validation was then performed through bench testing with varying exhaust flow rates. The model predictions aligned closely with the measured values, yielding a root mean square error of 0.007. The average error was 2.79%, with a maximum error of 4.93%. This comparison confirms that the calibrated k_{w0} is accurate.

4.1.3. Simulation of dynamic filtration process

After determining the wall permeability, simulations of the soot filtration process within the DPF can be performed under various operational conditions.

Fig. 6. Calibration results of clean wall permeability

Increased load positively influences the rate of PM loading. However, the actual PM loading process is lengthy. For instance, in this study, with a DPF bulk volume of 3.9 L, achieving each soot load of 1 g/L would take more than 3.9 hours, even with a maximum loading rate of 0.6 mg/s and a filtration efficiency of 100%. To streamline simulation time, three operating conditions were selected: a constant torque of 250 Nm with engine speeds of 1000 rpm, 1800 rpm, and 2400 rpm.

The variation in the saturation coefficient, θ_{sat} , is illustrated, showing that deep-bed filtration dominated the initial stage of the loading process. As particle agglomeration occurred and soot bridges formed, cake filtration began to take over. This shift is evidenced by a sharp rise in the saturation coefficient, which eventually approached 1, signaling that cake filtration efficiency had reached its peak. Additionally, a higher PM flow rate led to a faster convergence to saturation. At engine speeds of 1000 rpm and 1800 rpm, θ_{sat} reached saturation at 513 s and 4263 s, respectively. However, at an engine speed of 2400 rpm, where the PM flow rate was less than half of that at 1000 rpm, θ_{sat} had not reached saturation throughout the entire simulated period of 18000 s.

The dynamic filtration model demonstrated significantly improved prediction accuracy during both the transitional loading phase (soot load < 0.7 g/L) and the later loading phase (soot load > 2.1 g/L). This enhancement is due to the inclusion of two important factors in the model. First, it accounts for the gradual saturation process of the porosity-varying wall during the transitional stage. Second, it considers continuous in-wall filtration after the complete formation of the cake layer. Without these considerations, the predicted pressure drop results would otherwise be either overestimated or underestimated.

4.2. Filtration behaviour exploration

The impact of key structural and operational parameters—such as channel characteristics, monolithic size, and exhaust conditions—on DPF filtration efficiency and pressure drop performance was analyzed using an established lumped model. Table 6 presents the initial conditions for each case. Specifically, filtration efficiencies across different phases and the composition of various pressure drop components were chosen as the observed variables.

4.2.1. Influence of channel characteristics on filtration performance

The impact of different cell densities (ranging from 200 to 300 and 400 cpsi) and wall thicknesses (0.18, 0.28, and 0.38 mm, i.e., 7, 11, and 15 mil, respectively) on the filtration efficiency of the DPF is illustrated, it can be observed that when the wall thickness is fixed (0.18 mm), the overall filtration efficiency of the DPF improves as the cell density increases. This is because a higher number of channels results in decreased overall porosity and average pore size of the substrate, which aids in the PM trapping. Nevertheless, it is important to note that this effect on the cake filtration efficiency is the opposite of the overall efficiency. As more channels are present, the deposition of particles in each individual channel reduces, leading to a decrease in cake layer thickness and filtration efficiency. Moreover, it is interesting that the cake filtration efficiency initially surpasses the overall efficiency. As a result of the low deep-bed filtration efficiency, there is a slow accumulation rate of soot within the DPF wall, resulting in very limited deposition. Therefore, the overall efficiency is constrained and takes a longer time to approach or exceed the cake filtration efficiency.

After analysing, it is evident that while keeping the cell density fixed at 250 cpsi, the overall filtration efficiency of the DPF marginally improves with an increase in wall thickness, which is consistent with the findings of [26]. It can be found that altering the wall thickness predominantly influences the deep-bed filtration process, but has minimal impact on cake filtration. A larger wall thickness results in an increased particle deposition within the wall, leading to a notable improvement in deep-bed filtration efficiency. Nevertheless, this improvement makes only a tiny contribution to the total collected PM mass.

Table 6

Initial condition for the simulating cases.

Case	σ /cpsi	ω_w /mm	L/mm	D/mm	$T_{DPF,in}/^{\circ}C$	Q_v /kg-h ⁻¹
1-3	200-300-400	0.19	140.7	257.7	345	1160
4-6	300	0.19-0.29-0.39	140.7	257.7	345	1160
7-9	300	0.19	140.5-190.5-230.5	257.7	345	1160
10-12	300	0.19	140.7	257.7-266.7-295.8	345	1160
13-15	300	0.19	140.7	257.7	165-240-345	1160
16-18	300	0.19	140.7	257.7	345	648-850-1350

On the other hand, an increase in wall thickness amplifies the effect of deep-bed filtration, resulting in a significant increase in wall layer pressure drop and subsequently, the total pressure drop. However, an increase in wall thickness has little impact on cake filtration. When the wall thickness increases from 0.19 mm to 0.29 mm and 0.39 mm, the total pressure drop increases by 40.2 % and 94.7 % respectively, while the cake pressure drop only increases by 4.3 % and 9.9 % respectively. This suggests that the DPF wall thickness should not be too large, as it would result in a significant pressure drop at the expense of minimal improvement in PM loading capacity. Therefore, precise manufacturing techniques of the honeycomb porous ceramic substrate are essential for the reliability of the aftertreatment, and even the engine system [59].

4.2.2. Influence of monolithic size on filtration performance

The influence of different DPF lengths (140.5–190.5–230.5 mm) and diameters (257.7–266.7–295.8 mm, i.e., 8–9.5–11 in.) on DPF filtration efficiency. It is evident that the overall DPF filtration efficiency slightly improves with increasing length. This improvement can be attributed to the lower flow velocity, which favors PM deposition. However, this increase in filtration efficiency is not significant under the same exhaust condition.

It can be observed that widening the channels leads to an increase in wall filtration efficiency. However, the decrease in cake layer thickness results in a decrease in cake layer filtration efficiency and finally, there is a slight improvement in overall filtration efficiency. Hence, increasing the DPF filtering volume can enhance filtration, and compared to length, diameter has a greater influence on filtration efficiency.

The relationship between the size of the DPF and the pressure drop performance is illustrated. When the diameter of the DPF remains constant and the length increases, the airflow path becomes longer, leading to an increase in flow velocity and a significant increase in pressure drop along the channel. However, even though the mass of a single cake layer in the channel remains unchanged at the same PM loading level, the thickness of the cake layer decreases, resulting in an increase in the effective filtration area and a decrease in filtration velocity. Consequently, both the pressure drop of the cake layer and the wall layer decrease as the length of the DPF increases from 140.5 mm to 180.5 mm and 230.5 mm. Specifically, the pressure drop of the cake layer decreases by 40.6 % and 55.0 % respectively, while the wall layer pressure drop decreases by 30.3 % and 42.1 % respectively. However, the total pressure drop only decreases by 5.2 % and 3.1 % respectively, which is resulted from the trade-off between the frictional and Darcy's pressure drop contribution.

The influence of DPF inlet temperature and exhaust mass flow rate on the pressure drop performance. When the exhaust mass flow rate remains constant, increasing the DPF inlet temperature leads to an increase in exhaust volume flow rate and gas velocity, resulting in higher total pressure drop and individual component pressure drops. Among these components, the channel frictional pressure drop and wall layer pressure drop show a greater increase, contributing to a higher proportion of the total pressure drop. Specifically, increasing the DPF inlet temperature from 145°C to 220°C and 295°C results in a 43.4 % and 33.1 % increase in total pressure drop, respectively.

5. Conclusions

This study introduces a filtration-pressure drop model to effectively assess deposition status within the Diesel Particulate Filter (DPF) and to support efficient regeneration processes. The model captures the dynamic process of particulate matter (PM) filtration, while the impacts of structural and operational parameters on filtration efficiency and pressure drop characteristics were also explored. The main findings of this study are as follows:

1. Compared to the original model, this model achieved a reduction in the average and maximum pressure drop prediction errors by up to 9.40% and 17.25%, respectively. The dynamic filtration model also demonstrated superior prediction accuracy during both the transitional phase (soot loading < 0.6 g/L) and the later loading stage (soot loading > 2 g/L).
2. Increasing cell density enhances the overall filtration efficiency of the DPF, though this improvement diminishes as wall thickness increases. Optimal performance in pressure drop and PM loading can be attained by selecting an appropriate cell density, but excessive wall thickness should be avoided. While it may slightly increase PM loading capacity, it leads to a significant pressure drop. A longer DPF length slightly boosts overall filtration efficiency due to reduced gas velocity.

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